

PEDAGOGICAL SCIENCES

THE ROLE OF AGE IN SECOND LANGUAGE LEARNING

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Abstract

The article elaborates the age factor in teaching a foreign language. The advantages and disadvantages of early and late second language learning have been scrutinized in the study. The article notes that it is more efficient to learn the second language between the ages of 2-12. Since the learners at this age can easily possess listening skills while in later periods of age to master this skill becomes harder. Besides, it has been determined that kids they cannot comprehend grammar rules like the adults. The adults easily understand complex and compound sentences with their complicated grammatical structures while children find it difficult.

Keywords: age factor, comprehension, second language acquisition, language learning, cognition.

We all know that age is an important factor in language acquisition. Time to time, age was considered to be a problem for language learners. Different factors including native language, biological reasons, learning environment, emotions, intelligence, motivation play an indispensable role in effective language assimilation and the age factor is one of the factors that has a considerable impact on second language learning.

Babayev Javid underlines the importance of consideration of age and other factors in teaching process: "Teachers should approach and assess the students individually or taking their age, occupation and psychological conditions into consideration" [1, p.102].

As to Singleton and Ryan, the students that start to learn a foreign language in the childhood can obtain a higher level of proficiency than those who start later. It is evident that this idea contributes to the hypothesis to begin second language instruction earlier. It looks as a good beginning for the young students to hold the opportunities to study foreign language with early immersion to the foreign language instruction.

English began to be taught at fifth grade as a required course at the secondary school in 1990s. English teaching programs were modified again requiring English courses to start in the third form at the secondary schools around 2000. As time changes, the new policy stresses the significance of early start in foreign language teaching programs at an early age. The Chinese government has been underlining the the English language as a foreign language as a compulsory and vital curriculum at school recently. For this reason, English is actually taught in the first grade of the secondary school. Another important point should be touched upon that more nursery schools in rich cities start to teach English at the ages of 3 or 4 in the country.

All these positive changes about the policy of foreign language teaching presents that instruction of foreign language attracts the attention to carry out foreign language instruction earlier. Early second language learning motivates the kids to study the foreign language based on kids' personality. Generally speaking, they mostly show their interest to some new things but learning the first language. For this reason, if second language instruction is carried out at secondary school earlier, it will help to improve children's attitude on the

second language acquisition. They will demonstrate their self-consciousness and awareness about the cultural differences while being immersed into the foreign language learning. Subsequently, foreign language learning should be introduced to school as soon as possible, because it is better for kids to be exposed to the foreign language and ease their language learning process.

The advantages of early second language learning

To become a bilingual in early childhood is an unconscious phenomenon as natural as leaning to walk. According to scientific surveys, pronunciation and intonation may be learnt more easily in childhood and adolescence. It occurs when neuromuscular mechanisms are active until the age of 12. Another explanation why children's pronunciations are accent-free is their ability of imitation. The so-called ability vanishes considerably after puberty. Other factors which we should take into account are kid's spontaneity, tolerance and flexibility to new practice. Children are more eager to interact with people compared to adults. They are more keen on everything and they are not scared of making errors. They overcome hardships very easily by utilizing creative methods to interact such as non-verbal tools of interaction and use of onomatopoeic words. Besides, the thought of foreign civilization has not shaped in their views yet. They comprehend cultural and ethnic differences only at the age of eight. Memory capacity is another advantage in early language acquisition. There are researches showing the risk of semi-lingualism and recommending the parents to conduct language leaning planning carefully.

Researches reveal that learning a foreign language develops problem-solving, critical-thinking and listening skills. Furthermore, it improves memory, concentration and ability to multitask. Kids accomplished in other languages also show signs of mental flexibility and enhanced creativity. Kids that learn the second language before the age of 5 use the same part of their brains to learn the foreign language which they also use to acquire their native language. Younger students don't have the sense of fear of making errors which is a hindrance for the adults in most cases.

The time a student devotes to learn a foreign language has a positive and direct correlation with cognitive development. Longer orders also provide the chance for the students to grow up alongside the extra language and culture developing a more profound relation as they grow older.

It also boosts their academic achievement. The benefits of learning a foreign language at an early age have a direct affect on a kid's academic success. In comparison with those who don't know another language, bilingual kids have boosted writing, reading and math skills and they usually score higher points in tests.

Early language learning nurtures the children's curiosity, empathy, cultural sensitivity. Kids who are exposed to another language earlier show more positive attitudes to other cultures linked to that language.

The advantages of late second language learning

Firstly, it is essential to identify that we consider learning a language after puberty by late second language acquisition. Psychologists, linguists and pedagogues have been striving for many years to reply the following question: can we reach native-like proficiency while learning a language after puberty? To respond the question, we should take the following factors into consideration: Primarily, adults have an essential advantage: cognitive maturity and experience of the language system generally. By means of their knowledge of their native languages, they can both obtain more advantageous learning environment and can easily understand grammatical rules. As to Klein Dimorth, language learning is an accumulative process which enables us to build on existing knowledge. Kids are unable to acquire complex morphological and syntactical rules easily [3].

From perspective of kids' apparent success, a reason suggested in the 1970s that there is a critical period to learn a second language and it is before puberty. Hence, once the students passed this period, changes in the cognitive abilities and brain make the language acquisition more complicated. This is called critical-period hypothesis which brought about the arguments by some linguists which suggests to begin second language acquisition earlier. It is a pity that a great deal of researches dedicated to this topic has not verified that theory that the younger are better language learners. It is undeniable that the juveniles have some advantages in some aspects of language learning, especially in pronunciation. So the students who commence to learn the foreign language at an early age often grasp foreign accent very quickly.

It will be useful to demonstrate that wrong pronunciation is not sometimes an issue of ability but of good determination. As to various questionnaires, elderly people don't feel like themselves while speaking a foreign language and they think that pronunciation is an ethno-linguistic identity maker. A positive and negative attitude about a foreign language acquisition must not be underestimated. Adult's motivation to study a foreign language is another factor to take into account. When an adult decides to study a foreign language, there are some reasons for this such as education

abroad, promotion at workplace, social integration, social prestige, residential purposes, etc. The last is regarded a very grounded one, particularly in the case of immigrants who intend to change their dwelling places.

We all know that the language learning process in children and adults own merits and demerits. Nevertheless, age is an essential but not overriding factor in language acquisition. All learners, irrespective of their ages, comprehend a language learning process individually and differently. Talent, ability and personality may impact this process considerably. For example, there can be timid kids and very sociable adults. To encourage a language learning at an early age is expedient. The younger the kid is, the more he/she can benefit from neuromuscular systems which develop language acquisition. They can reach a native-like level with a little attempt and time in this case. The advantages as excellent accent, increased communication skills and tolerance to personal cognitive development and foreign cultures are included in benefits of early language learning. However, effective language acquisition in adults is not excluded here. Everyone may reach a proficient language level under good language learning environment with motivation and positive attitude.

Yet, there are numerous factors apart from the age. The children also get profits and rewards for their attempts because learning a new language is the key to the acceptance of the peer and to satisfaction of fundamental needs. These factors are not the same for the adults who learn English in the classroom. Dornyei shows that there are numerous factors involved in any circumstance and the age is just one of them [2]. But it should not be considered to be the most important. We can also find proofs of unsuccessful infant language acquisition, simultaneously successful adult language learning. Adults can experience some advantages to some extent, since there is proof for distinctions in the ways older and younger students approach language acquisition. Older students are especially skillful at learning vocabulary. For instance, they can utilize more different cognitive skills compared to children. Because they can use more abstract thinking and reasoning and are able to learn something reflectively and analytically.

After making a research about this challenge, we came to such a conclusion that foreign language learning is more effective between the ages of 2 and 12. The comprehension of the language in this period is spontaneous unlike the adults. It turned out that kids can develop their pronunciation skills efficiently like native-speakers. However, they cannot perceive grammar rules like the adults and children are unable to learn the words as fast as adult learners. Adult students can understand complex and compound sentences better than kids due to their vast cognitive and logical ability. In general, it is possible to claim that it is better to learn a language at an early age rather than in adultery years. Because to learn a foreign language in later period of life, even though you learn it proficiently, makes an adult learner feel strange while speaking the second language. But kids accept the foreign language as a native language while learning it simultaneously with his/her native language

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